

Soils over Calcareous Rocks in Golo Burdo Mountain

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Received: 17 July 2021

Accepted: 1 October 2021

Abstract

The paper deals with calcareous soils in Golo Bardo Mountain in western Bulgaria. Until now no significant studies have been made for the soils of Golo Bardo Mountain. Our goal was to give assess data for their soil features, characteristics, main diagnostic indicators and properties in order to define the soil formation processes, as well as their complete morphological description. Eight soil profiles were studied in different parts of the mountain. Due to the carbonate soil-forming rocks, the leaching processes in these soils are extremely weak and it is usually difficult to distinguish the individual genetic horizons. In relation to the soil-forming carbonate rocks in the area, we distinguish two main soil units. The studied soils are Leptosols or Phaeozems with good fine-granular structure, dark humus horizon (mollic) and shallow soil profile Ak-ACK-CRk, lying on hard or weathered carbonate rock. In the studied mountain area with different elevation, the surface mollic horizon is usually shallower and very often eroded with fragments from calcareous rock. The soils are well stocked with organic matter. The amount of organic carbon in the surface A horizon varied from 7.4 % to 2.8%.

The calcium dominates in exchange capacity of the soil over all other cations. There is no exchange acidity in these soils, except small amounts in the soil surface and in litter. The content of carbonates is an important soil-forming feature of these soils.

Keywords: Leptosols, Phaeozems, carbonates, soil properties

Introduction

Golo Bardo Mountain rises is located between the towns of Pernik and Radomir and their valleys. The mountain is a part of the “Verilo-Rui” mountain range, the formation of which began at the end of the Mesozoic period, intensified during the Tertiary, when the current mountain was formed and continues to present days. It is composed mainly of Triassic sandstone, marl, limestone, conglomerates and etc. (Geography of Bulgaria, 2002). Carbonate rich content of the soil-forming rocks is with particular importance for determining the soil-forming process. Soil formation and distribution are mainly related to the chemical and mineral composition of the carbonate parent rock as well as to its physical, chemical and mineral properties (Donov, 1993; Ilinkin et al. 2017; Malinova et al., 2018; Teoharov, 2019). The main soil unit of this area is Rendzina, which could be classified as Rendzic Leptosols and Rendzic Phaeozems (IUSS Working group 2015).

According to Belivanova (1997), the main diagenetic processes that have affected the Triassic carbonate rocks are discussed in this study: transformation of metastable carbonates (aragonite and high-magnesium calcite) into calcite; compaction; cementation; recrystallization; authigenic mineral formation (dolomitization, silicification, albitization and pyritization). The Triassic sediments in Golo Bardo are incorporated in several groups: the Petrohan Terrigenous group, the Iskar Carbonate Group, and a very limited Moesian Terrigenous- Carbonate Group, which is out of the area of the section (Ilieva, 2017).

The soils from the area of Golo Bardo Mountain are formed under forest meadows, bushes and trees vegetation. As a typical mountainous terrain, surface horizons are subjected to erosion processes. The properties and composition of the studied soils and the degree of their fertility depend a lot on the type and age of the parent rocks, on the relief, exposure, latitude and altitude.

As well as on the impact of climatic conditions that activate or suppress more or less biological activity and determine the state and biological potential of soil cover (Koinov, 1947).

In the semi-mountainous areas, shallow forest soils have been developed on weathered hard rocks such as Rendzic and Clacarcic Leptosols, and in many places they are also found in a complex with Endoclastic Phaeozems. Leptosols have a shallow profile (up to 30 cm) and often rocks on the surface. These soils occupy mostly rugged (erosion-hazardous) steep terrains and they are particularly not important for agriculture. The vegetation which is developing on them is mainly mixed forests. There are also coniferous trees, as well as shrubby, meadow-grass and in some areas - mosses and lichens. The soils are usually distributed in the foothills and mountainous areas of Golo Bardo and they are subjected to gully erosion.

Figure 1. Golo Burdo Mountain – district of Pernik, Bulgaria

The anthropogenic impact play a key role for the genesis, structure and fertility of these soils. This includes deforestation, construction in forest areas, stone quarries, excavation of mountain areas for coal and other minerals, road construction and permanent pollution. From Golo Bardo mountain are produced raw materials such as limestone and dolomite, used for cement production. Sand quarries have been discovered in several places near rivers.

The aim of the study is to establish the contemporary development of the soils on Triassic carbonate sediments and to describe their main morphological, chemical and physical properties.

Material and Methods

To establish the criteria and diagnostics for the classification of Rendzinas – Rendzic Leptosols and Rendzic Phaeozems (IUSS Working group, 2015), in this article we used previous data from studies in the area of Golo Bardo mountain. In addition to in-depth geomorphological and morphological studies, analytical results are given on various diagnostic indicators.

Eight soil profiles were studied in the different parts of the mountain. The analysis of soil samples was performed according to the following indicators, criteria and methods: Morphological description of soil horizons and characteristics (Teoharov et al. 2019, Guidelines for soil description, Jahn, et al., 2006). Soil texture by Kachniski (1958), transformed to USDA classes; Total carbon according to Tyurin (Kononova, 1966); Total nitrogen according to Keldal (Penkov et al., 1991); total carbonates by the Scheibler (Penkov et al., 1991); Cation exchange capacity, exchange cations and degree of base saturation (Ganev and Arsova, 1980). Ammonia and nitrate nitrogen by Bremner and Keeney (1966); the mobile forms of phosphorus and potassium by the acetate-lactate method of Ivanov (1984) and pH and EC, in water with combined “pH and EC device”, Microsoft Excel (2010) is used for figures and statistics.

Results and Discussion

Clacareous soils spread in the mountain such as Rendzic or Calcaric Leptosols and Endocalcic Phaeozems, are soils are rich in carbonates (up to 52 %, Table 2) but also with high organic carbon content due to alkaline reaction, in which the decomposition of organic matter is slow and the soil accumulates high amounts of stable organic matter (Table 1). Their rich carbonate content is due to Triassic calcareous sediments over which they were developed (limestone, dolomite, marl, etc.). In previous edition of FAO (1988) classification these soils were known as Rendzinas.

Due to the carbonate soil-forming rocks, the leaching processes in these soils are extremely weak and it is usually difficult to distinguish the individual genetic horizons. In relation to the soil-forming carbonate rocks in the area, we distinguish two main units of these soils in Figure 1. The geologic or lithological nature of the parent material was considered to be the most important soil forming factor in determining the type of soil formation (Handley, 1954).

The profiles 1 and 8 are classified as Rendzic Leptosol which are characterized by a good fine-granular structure dark humus horizon (mollic) up to 15-20 cm and shallow soil profile Ak-ACk-CRk with a thickness of 20-40 (up to 75) cm, directly lying on hard or

weathered carbonate rock. In the studied area of the mountain with different elevations, the surface mollic horizon is usually shallower and very often eroded with fragments from parent rock. The other Leptosols are Skeletic Calcaric Leptosol in most of them with shallow mollic horizons (IUSS Working group, 2015).

Figure 2. Calcareous soils from Golo Bardo Mountain. Profile 8 - Rendzic Leptosol (on the left) and Profile 3 – Endocalcic Phaeozem loamic (on the right).

Leptosols are highly incoherent while Phaeozems are highly coherent, leading to the conclusion that the physical and chemical properties of the soil profiles of Phaeozems are specific (Radmanovic et al., 2020).

Phaeozems are deep soils from 70 to 120 cm soil profile with A1(Ak1)–Ak2-ACk-Ck-R structure and usually thick surface mollic horizon. These soils have primary carbonates from weathering rock. Most of the soil profiles they are leached in depth, but not anywhere. Mollic horizon is well formed, dark colored with fine granular structure and deeper about up to 30-50 cm. In whole profile stony fragments from parent rock could be found also. Phaeozems are spread usually in the low accumulative part of the mountains, so called foothills and land pockets. In such areas soil erosion is weak and consequently deep soil profiles could develop.

The soils are well stocked with organic matter, under the influence of forests vegetation. The amount of organic carbon in the surface A horizon is between 7.4 % and 2.8%. The mean value of org. C is 3.28 % in all soil horizons (Table 3). These soils are developed under dry conditions where organic carbon accumulation is greater than decomposition as a result of the limestone-rich environment, and where a portion of the organic component might be derived from residues of bedrock weathering (Schreier et al.,

1985). The temperate climatic conditions create a favorable condition for intensive humification with the formation of good quality humus (Hristov et al., 2017; 2021) .

Table 1. Main soil chemical and physical properties.

Horizon Depth (cm)	Total org. C %	Total N %	C/N	Carbo- nates, %	NH ₄ +NO ₃ mg/kg	P ₂ O ₅ mg/100g	K ₂ O mg/100g	Soil texture in mm			
								Sand >0.05	Silt 0.05- 0.002	Clay <0.002	
Profile 1. Rendzic Leptosol loamic											
1	Ak 0-5	7.14	0.41	17.54	25.3	37.4	3.4	36.8	40.5	38.5	21
2	ACk1 25-20	2.53	0.25	9.92	38.4	23.0	1.2	22.1	39.1	40.95	19.95
3	ACk2 20-38	1.26	0.15	8.23	40.3	20.2	1.4	8.3	44.7	38.45	16.85
4	Ck 38-70	0.5	0.06	8.33	51.7	19	4.8	6.5	35.1	43.55	21.35
Profile 2. Skeletic Calcaric Leptosol loamic											
5	ARk 0-19	5.35	0.46	11.5	5.06	23.0	0.23	51.9	36.5	39.7	23.8
Profile 3. Endocalcic Phaeozem loamic											
6	Ak1 0-10	6	0.6	10.03	6.96	9.79	0.32	71	53.2	28.65	18.15
7	Ak2 10-22	3.4	0.41	8.35	14.7	21.3	0.23	47.6	54.1	29.65	16.25
8	Ak3 22-43	2.89	0.35	8.16	16.49	23.0	0.21	20.6	52.7	28.9	18.4
9	ACk 43-60	1.97	0.23	8.38	19.44	21.3	0.21	9.8	50.5	30.15	19.35
10	Ck 60-100	1.14	0.12	9.57	29.4	20.2	0.22	6	48.7	29.85	21.45
Profile 4. Mollic Calcaric Leptosol loamic											
11	A 0-10	7.8	0.49	16.01	1.18	17.3	0.24	23.6	52.9	30	17.1
12	ACk 10-28	4.08	0.38	10.59	1.29	19.0	0.23	15.7	47.7	35.2	17.1
13	CRk 28-70	2.86	0.35	8.19	3.85	17.8	0.21	34.6	49.3	32.1	18.6
Profile 5. Skeletic Calcaric Leptosol loamic											
14	ARk0-14	3.47	0.35	10.26	10.26	19.0	0.3	10.2	52.3	29.25	18.45
Profile 6. Cambic Mollic Calcaric Leptosol clayic											
15	Ak 0 - 5	2.68	0.27	9.93	2.25	22.5	1.3	26.8	14.7	35.1	50.2
16	ACk1 5 -30	1.85	0.20	9.25	23.41	10.9	0.21	14.9	35.8	19.55	44.65
17	ACk2 30-50	2.09	0.21	9.95	21.55	20.2	0.23	13.5	31.7	22.9	45.4
18	Ck 50 - 75	1.13	0.14	8.07	24.04	15.6	0.3	8.7	29.5	20.95	49.25
Profile 7. Endocalcic Phaeozem clayic											
19	Ak 0 - 9	6.63	0.52	12.75	2.25	13.2	0.3	55.1	51.1	18.75	30.15
20	Ak2 9 -32	4.2	0.39	10.77	4.9	8.60	0.8	32.8	46.9	14.85	38.25
21	ACk1 32-45	3.29	0.34	9.68	12.26	14.4	1.6	22.4	53.4	14.9	31.7
22	ACk2 45-61	2.86	0.29	9.86	10.51	23.6	1.4	20.8	48.1	13.05	38.85
23	Ck1 61 - 90	2.36	0.23	10.26	18.77	15.5	1.2	18.5	34.2	17.55	48.25
24	Ck2 90-120	2.09	0.22	9.50	22.58	11.5	0.9	23	39.2	18.15	42.65
Profile 8. Rendzic Leptosol											
25	Ak 0 -11	5.33	0.51	10.45	18.77	12.1	0.1	33.5	42.9	17.05	40.05
26	ACk 11 -30	3.52	0.37	9.51	20.63	9.2	0.3	30	50.6	12	37.4
27	Ck 30 - 75	0.4	0.05	8.00	43.1	11.5	1.6	5	51.6	12.05	36.35

Table 2. Cation exchange capacity of exchange cations, base saturation and electrical conductivity.

Horizon / Depth cm	pH / H ₂ O	EC mS/cm	CEC	Ex. H _{8.2}	Ex. Al	Ex. Ca	Ex. Mg	Base Saturation %	
									mequ / 100g soil
Profile 1. Rendzic Mollic Leptosol loamic									
1	Ak 0-5	6.7	0.105	40.6	2.2	0.0	36.8	2.5	94.58
2	ACk 5-20	7.25	0.098	30.0	1.0	0.0	26.5	3.0	96.67
3	ACk ₂ 20-38	7.5	0.077	26.0	0.0	0.0	22.2	3.8	100.00
4	Ck 38-70	7.65	0.07	25.0	0.0	0.0	21.2	3.8	100.00
Profile 2. Skeletic Calcaric Leptosol loamic									
5	ARk 0-19	7.0	0.098	48.4	1.6	0.0	43.5	3.8	96.69
Profile 3. Endocalcic Phaeozem loamic									
6	Ak ₁ 0-10	7.0	0.105	45.8	2.0	0.0	39.5	4.8	95.63
7	Ak ₂ 10-22	7.25	0.126	38.8	1.0	0.0	33.8	4.2	97.42
8	Ak ₃ 22-43	7.40	0.119	36.7	0.0	0.0	32.2	4.5	100.00
9	ACk 43-60	7.40	0.112	30.6	0.0	0.0	26.1	4.5	100.00
10	Ck 60-100	7.50	0.084	30.6	0.0	0.0	25.6	5.0	100.00
Profile 4. Mollic Calcaric Leptosol loamic									
11	A 0-10	6.6	0.07	44.2	4.1	0.0	35.6	4.6	90.72
12	ACk 10-28	7.1	0.084	47.1	2.0	0.0	40.8	4.8	95.75
13	CRk 28-70	7.4	0.091	36.0	0.0	0.0	31.0	5.0	100.00
Profile 5. Skeletic Calcaric Leptosol loamic									
14	ARk 0-14	7.4	0.091	49.6	0.0	0.0	44.8	4.8	100.00
Profile 6. Cambic Mollic Calcaric Leptosol clayic									
15	Ak ₁ 0 - 5	7.4	0.098	26.0	0.0	0.0	24.8	1.2	100.0
16	ACk 5 -30	7.4	0.091	25.9	0.0	0.0	24.6	1.3	100.0
17	ACk 30 -50	7.4	0.098	26.3	0.0	0.0	25.0	1.3	100.0
18	Ck 50 - 75	7.5	0.084	26.7	0.0	0.0	25.4	1.3	100.0
Profile 7. Endocalcic Phaeozem clayic									
19	Ak ₁ 0 - 9	7.2	0.168	48.6	1.0	0.0	42.0	5.6	97.94
20	Ak ₂ 9 -32	7.4	0.126	48.6	0.0	0.0	42.5	6.1	100.0
21	ACk 32-45	7.4	0.105	39.0	0.0	0.0	33.0	6.0	100.0
22	ACk ₂ 45- 61	7.4	0.091	37.8	0.0	0.0	32.0	5.8	100.0
23	Ck 61 - 90	7.4	0.105	36.8	0.0	0.0	30.6	6.2	100.0
24	Ck ₂ 90 - 120	7.4	0.126	33.8	0.0	0.0	27.8	6.0	100.0
Profile 8. Rendzic Leptosol									
25	Ak 0 -11	7.4	0.119	41.8	0.0	0.0	37.0	4.8	100.0
26	ACk 11 -30	7.4	0.105	32.6	0.0	0.0	28.0	4.6	100.0
27	Ck 30 - 75	8.0	0.077	18.6	0.0	0.0	14.6	4.0	100.0

Soils developed over hard carbonate rocks, in contrast to other soils, have more specific distribution of carbonates. For example, the amount of carbonates in the whole profile varies from 1.2 to 52.2 % (Table 1 and 3). This suggests that the carbonate plate has a primary terrigenous origin. The reaction of these soils is alkaline (pH in water has the highest levels in the carbonate plate). Studied soils have from neutral reaction (6.7) up to slightly alkaline reaction (8.0). The reason for that is high content of carbonates. The pH is usually above 7, but in surface horizon sometimes it is lower because of high content of organic litter especially under pine forest trees (Table 2).

Figure 3. Soil organic carbon, total carbonates, and particle sizes content.

The soil mean pH = 7.33, could define as carbonate, very slightly alkaline. Compared to the colloidal reactivity (the mean value of CEC = 36.6 mequ/100g) is medium colloidal clay, with evolution to montmorillonite clay (Ganev et al., 1990). This determines the presence of alkaline carbonates and the active hydrolysis-alkaline adsorption salt composed of strongly based alkaline cations (Ca and Mg) and weakly acidic ion exchangers (mainly H⁺).

Figure 4. Soil texture in all soil horizons and profiles.

The total nitrogen varies from 0.60 to 0.35 %, in surface horizons which good reserve. Well known fact is that approximately 98% -99% of nitrogen is found in the soil in the form of organic nitrogen compounds (mainly in humus) and only 1% -2% - as available for plants nitrates and ammonium salts.

Figure 5. Main physicochemical properties and soil pH (in blue).

Mobile forms of NH_4 and NO_3 are about from 37 to 8.6 mg/kg which is low. The reason for that is high content of carbonates and mobile forms of NH_4 , NO_3 and P_2O_5 are blocked. Only available K_2O has high content (mean value about 25 kg/100g), which is typical for weathered mountain soils in Bulgaria.

The type of humus according to C:N ratio is Mull (<14). This type is characterized by of forests, or grasslands with humid climates. The porous, crumbly humus rapidly decomposes and becomes well mixed into the mineral soil, so that distinct layers are not apparent. Where free CaCO_3 occurred in the Ak-horizon, a mull forest horizon had developed even on coarse sand and the associated herb flora differed only slightly from that occurring on very acid mull. Mulls generally form under trees with more nutrient-rich litter, where gut-passage through soil animals followed by predominantly bacterial decomposition creates granular structures (Delecour, 1980). The soil texture is mainly loamy, sandy-clay and clay (Figure 4). The silt fraction is lower than other two fractions (Table 3). The highest mean value of the soil texture is sand with about 44 % with additional skeletal content. Sandy soils with a higher skeletal content are the soils developed on marble (Filcheva et al., 2014). Usually these soils are loose, warm and well-aerated. A significant part of them have an unfavorable water regime due to their shallow profile. In most areas there are rocks on the surface. The studied soils developed over Triassic carbonate plate are characterized by good physical properties.

The content of carbonates varies in a fairly wide range (1.8-50%). In order to be classified as Rendzinas (Rendzic), soil-forming materials must contain more than 40%

carbonates. Profile 1 and 8 have Rendzic properties according WRB (IUSS working group, 2015). The mean $\text{pH}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ value ~ 7.45 determines the presence of alkaline carbonates and the active hydrolysis-alkaline adsorption salt, composed of strongly basic alkaline earth cations and a weakly acidic ion exchanger. There is no exchange acidity in these soils, except small amounts in the soil surface and in litter (figure 5).

Table 3. Main descriptive statistic values of studied soil profiles.

	pH H ₂ O	EC	CEC	ex. H	ex Al	ex Ca	ex. Mg	B.S. %	Org C
Mean	7.33	0.10	36.00	0.55	0	31.4	4.20	98.7	3.29
Stand. Err.	0.05	0.00	1.70	0.20	0	1.49	0.29	0.45	0.38
Median	7.40	0.10	36.70	0.00	0	31.0	4.60	100	2.86
Mode	7.40	0.11	26.00	0.00	0	*	4.80	100	2.86
Stand. Dev.	0.27	0.02	8.85	1.02	0	7.73	1.53	2.33	1.98
Range	1.40	0.10	31.00	4.10	0	30.2	5.00	9.28	7.40
Minimum	6.60	0.07	18.60	0.00	0	14.6	1.20	90.7	0.40
Maximum	8.00	0.17	49.60	4.10	0	44.8	6.20	100	7.80
	Total N	C/N	Carbonates	NH ₄ +NO ₃	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	Sand	Silt	Clay
Mean	0.33	10.37	18.12	17.78	0.87	24.80	43.96	26.36	29.66
Stand. Err.	0.04	0.85	2.63	1.19	0.21	3.20	1.83	1.87	2.32
Median	0.35	9.57	18.77	19.00	0.30	22.10	47.70	28.90	23.80
Mode	0.41	0.00	2.25	23.00	0.23	*	*	*	17.10
Stand. Dev.	0.16	3.05	13.66	6.18	1.08	16.60	9.53	9.74	12.06
Range	0.54	9.38	50.52	28.80	4.70	66.00	39.40	31.55	33.95
Minimum	0.06	8.16	1.18	8.60	0.10	5.00	14.70	12.00	16.25
Maximum	0.60	17.54	51.70	37.40	4.80	71.00	54.10	43.55	50.20

Because of high carbonate content studied soils have high Base saturation (98.6 %). The calcium dominates in base saturation over all other cations. The content of carbonates is an important soil-forming feature of these soils, because it diagnoses the base excess, and which the process of soil formation and carbon sequestration take place (Ganev, 1989).

Conclusion

The soils of Golo Bardo mountain are Rendzic or Calcaric Leptosols and Endocalcic Phaeozems, with high organic carbon content with alkaline reaction. Decomposition of organic matter is slow and the soil accumulates high amounts of stable organic matter. Their rich carbonate content is due to Triassic calcareous sediments over which they were developed. The Leptosols are characterized by a good granular structure dark humus horizon (mollic) up to 15-20 cm and shallow soil profile type Ak-ACk-CRk with a thickness of 20-40 (up to 75) cm, lying on hard or weathered carbonate rock. Phaeozems are deep soils form 70 to 120 cm soil profile with A1(Ak1)–Ak2-ACk-Ck-R structure with usually thick surface mollic horizon that is well formed, dark colored with fine granular structure and deeper. The

type of humus according C:N ratio is Mull(<14). This type of humus is typical for forests, or grasslands in humid climates.

These soils have primary carbonates from weathering rock consequently they have high sorption capacity. The soil reaction varies from neutral and to slightly alkaline, with the high degree of base saturation. The calcium dominates in exchange capacity of the soil over all other cations. Soils have favorable properties due to good reserve of organic carbon, potassium, nitrogen and high base saturation

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